

The Enzymes in Snake Venom. Part. II. Their Action on Native Proteins, on Peptone and on the Activity of trypsin.

BY B. N. GHOSH AND S. S. DE.

It has been recorded by several authors, as early as 1902-1903 that snake venom contains proteolytic enzymes. The behaviour of these enzymes has not yet been fully investigated. Recently Masakazu Sato and Tamatsu Hirano (*Mem. Facult. Sci. Agric. Taihoku*, 1935, **9**, 83) have found that the venoms of some Formosan snakes can digest proteins and that their optimum activity lies between p_H 8.0 to p_H 8.5 depending on the nature of the substrate used.

In a previous paper it has been shown by one of us (Ghosh, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1936, **13**, 450), that the proteolytic enzyme in cobra (*Naja Naja*) venom resembles trypsin so far as its activity depends on the p_H of the substrate suspension. Since *Vipera Russellii* belongs to a group quite different from that of cobra, a study of the enzymes in its venom was undertaken.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Action of Russell's Viper Venom on Proteins.

The experimental procedure adopted was the same as described by Ghosh (*loc. cit.*) in a previous paper. Stock solutions (5%) of gelatin (electro-dialysed), Merck's dried egg-albumin and of casein were prepared and kept in a refrigerator with a few drops of toluene as preservative.

Solution of Russell's viper venom (1%) in 0.85% NaCl solution was prepared and its toxicity determined. It was found that 0.01 mg. of venom (dry weight) kills a pigeon weighing 300 g. when injected intravenously.

The stock protein solution (20 c.c.) was taken in an Erlenmeyer's flask and its p_H adjusted to the requisite value by adding a few drops of HCl or NaOH according to need. To this solution 10 c.c. of buffer solution of the same p_H were added. 10 C.c. of this buffered protein solution were placed in each of the two conical flasks. To one of the flasks, 2 c.c. of the venom solution and 8 c.c. of physiological saline

were added. To the other, which served as control, 10 c.c. of physiological saline only were added. After adding a few drops of toluene to each of the flasks, they were stoppered and placed in a thermostat at 36°. After suitable intervals of time, 5 c.c. portions of the solution were withdrawn from each set of flasks and added to 45 c.c. of absolute alcohol to which 0.5 c.c. of 0.5% thymolphthalein solution in alcohol was previously added. To the flask containing the 5 c.c. control sample, 0.5 c.c. of the venom solution were added just before titration. The interval of time allowed for digestion was 24 hours. The buffer solutions used are acid potassium phthalate from p_H 2.2 to p_H 5.8, acid potassium phosphate from p_H 6.0 to p_H 8.0 and boric acid and potassium chloride from p_H 8.2 to p_H 10. The results are recorded in Tables I—III.

TABLE I.

Substrate—Egg-albumin. Venom—Russell's viper.

0.0456 N alcoholic KOH required in c.c. for titration of 5 c.c. of the soln.

p_H .	Active venom and substrate.	Control.	Diff.	p_H .	Active venom and substrate.	Control.	Diff.
2.4	4.9	4.9	0.0	7.6	2.44	2.06	0.38
3.6	4.35	4.35	0.0	8.0	2.14	1.72	0.42
5.0	2.70	2.65	0.05	8.6	1.74	1.40	0.34
6.0	3.27	3.15	0.12	9.0	1.32	1.10	0.22
6.6	2.86	2.70	0.16	9.4	0.92	0.8	0.12
7.0	2.66	2.42	0.24				

TABLE II.

Substrate—Casein. Venom—Russell's viper.

0.0456 N-alcoholic KOH required in c.c. for titrating 5 c.c. of the soln.

p_H .	Active venom and substrate.	Control.	Diff.	p_H .	Active venom and substrate.	Control.	Diff.
5.0	3.04	2.92	0.12	7.6	2.95	2.35	0.60
6.0	4.09	3.74	0.35	8.0	2.21	1.70	0.51
6.6	3.76	3.22	0.54	8.6	1.74	1.35	0.39
7.0	3.38	2.76	0.62	9.0	1.24	0.95	0.29

TABLE III.

Substance—Gelatin.				Venom—Russell's viper.			
0.0456 <i>N</i> -alcoholic KOH required in c.c. for titrating 5 c.c. of soln.							
p_H	Active venom and substrate.	Control.	Diff.	p_H .	Active venom and substrate.	Control.	Diff.
5.0	1.75	1.64	0.11	8.0	1.60	1.12	0.48
6.0	2.24	2.06	0.18	8.6	1.42	0.98	0.44
6.6	2.01	1.76	0.25	9.0	1.24	0.90	0.34
7.0	1.85	1.54	0.31	9.4	0.98	0.78	0.20
7.6	1.75	1.30	0.45				

It will be noticed from the data recorded in the Tables I—III that the optimum activity of the protease in Russell's viper venom using gelatin and egg-albumin as substrates is at p_H 8.0 approximately, while with a casein suspension it is in the neighbourhood of p_H 7.0. The proteolytic enzymes in the venoms of cobra and Russell's viper thus resemble trypsin in so far as their activity depends on the p_H of the substrate suspension.

Action of the Venoms of Cobra and Russell's Viper on Peptone.

It has been recorded by Launey (*Compt. rend.*, 1902, 135, 401) that the disintegration of proteins like casein and serum albumin by the action of venoms of cobra and of the viper proceeds so far as to the stage of albumose. It never leads to the formation of peptone. It is not yet known whether the venoms of cobra or of Russell's viper can hydrolyse peptone to simpler compounds. The action of these venoms on solutions of Witte's peptone at different p_H was, therefore, investigated. The experimental procedure was the same as described before. The results are given in Tables IV and V.

TABLE IV.

Substrate—peptone. Venom—cobra.

0.0403 N-EtOH-KOP required for titrating 5 c.c. of the soln.

pH.	Active venom and substrate.	Control.	Diff.
6.0	5.94	5.54	0.40
6.5	5.14	4.68	0.46
7.0	4.62	4.08	0.54
7.6	3.78	3.12	0.66
8.0	3.26	2.56	0.70
8.6	2.67	1.95	0.72
9.0	2.20	1.52	0.68
9.4	1.80	1.24	0.56

TABLE V.

Substrate—peptone. Venom—Russell's viper.

0.0449 N-EtOH-KOH required for titrating 5 c.c. of soln.

pH.	Active venom and substrate.	Control.	Diff.
6.0	5.77	5.52	0.25
6.6	4.96	4.66	0.30
7.0	4.44	4.08	0.36
7.6	3.56	3.10	0.46
8.0	3.05	2.55	0.50
8.6	2.47	1.94	0.53
9.0	1.98	1.50	0.48
9.4	1.65	1.25	0.40

From an examination of the data in the Tables IV and V it appears that both the venoms can disintegrate Witte's peptone. For the same weight, the activity of cobra venom is greater than that of Russell's viper venom. The optimum activity of the peptidase in both the venoms is in the region of pH 8.2 to pH 8.5. This shows that the venoms contain an enzyme identical with or similar to erepsin.

Action of Snake Venom on the Activity of Trypsin.

Delezenne (*Compt. rend.*, 1902, 135, 329) studied the effect of snake venom on the proteolytic activity of pancreatic juice. It was found that although snake venom alone cannot digest egg-albumin coagulated by heat yet when it was added to inert pancreatic juice it led to the rapid digestion of the coagulated protein. On heating, to 100° for 15 minutes, it was found to have lost its power of activating the inert pancreatic juice. Delezenne (*loc. cit.*) therefore concluded that snake venom contains a kinase similar to enterokinase. Recently Delezenne's observation has been confirmed by Masakazu Stato and Tamotsu Hiyono (*Mem. Facult. Sci. Agric. Taihoku*, 1935, 9, 105); who used glycerol extract of pancreas instead of inactive pancreatic juice. In our experiments we tried the effect of venoms of cobra and Russell's viper on the activity of trypsin (Merck) to find out if they contain some trypsin activator. The experimental procedure adopted was the same as described already. Sets of flasks containing substrate only, substrate and 1 c.c. of 0.1% trypsin, substrate and 2 c.c. of 1% venom, and substrate, trypsin and venom, were placed in a thermostat at 36°. The final volume of the mixtures in each of the flasks was 20 c.c. and the concentration of the substrate was the same in all the flasks. The data are recorded below.

TABLE VI.

Venom—Russell's viper. Substrate—gelatin. Time—after 6 hours' incubation.

p _n .	0.0448 N-EtOH-KOH required for titrating 5 c.c. of soln.				
	Control.	Venom.	Trypsin.	Trypsin and venom.	Diff. between Columns 3 and 4.
6.0	2.08	2.13	3.04	2.2	0.84
7.0	1.58	1.65	2.94	1.74	1.20
7.6	1.32	1.44	2.84	1.52	1.32
8.5	1.02	1.12	2.28	1.22	1.06

TABLE VII.

Venom and substrate—same as in Table VI. Time—after 24 hours' incubation.

p _n .	0.0448 N-EtOH-KOH required for titrating 5 c.c. of the soln.				
	Control.	Venom.	Trypsin.	Trypsin and venom.	Diff. between columns 3 and 4.
6.0	2.10	2.30	3.95	2.52	1.43
7.0	1.58	1.90	4.10	2.40	1.70
7.6	1.34	1.78	4.04	2.24	1.80
8.5	1.00	1.42	3.46	1.76	1.70

TABLE VIII.

Venom—cobra. Substrate—gelatin. Time—after 24 hours incubation.

0.0441 N-EtOH-KOH required for titrating 5 c.c. of the soln.

p_H	Control	Venom	Trypsin	Trypsin and venom	Diff between columns 3 & 4.
6.0	2.28	2.56	3.94	3.00	0.94
7.0	1.70	2.18	4.03	2.82	1.21
7.6	1.45	2.00	3.95	2.75	1.20
8.5	1.10	1.62	3.42	2.35	1.07

TABLE IX.

Venom—Russell's viper Substrate—peptone (Witte). Time 24 hours' incubation

0.0422 N-EtOH-KOH required for titrating 5 c.c. of the soln.

p_H	Control	Venom	Trypsin	Trypsin and venom.	Diff between columns 3 & 4
6.0	5.06	5.26	6.38	5.71	0.67
7.0	3.72	4.04	5.73	4.94	0.79
7.6	2.85	3.25	5.11	4.30	0.81
8.5	1.85	2.33	4.15	3.41	0.74

It is evident from the data recorded above that the venoms used contain a trypsin inhibitor. It may be mentioned here that the activation of inert pancreatic juice by snake venom as observed by Delezenne (*loc. cit.*) can be accounted for without assuming the existence of enterokinase in the venom. Recently Northrop and co-workers (U. N. Science, 1933, 78) have shown that in pancreatic extract there is another proteolytic enzyme besides trypsinogen and this they termed chymotrypsinogen. They further showed that a trace of trypsin can convert inactive chymotrypsinogen to the active form chymotrypsin. Addition of snake venom, which we have already shown contains trypsin, to the inactive pancreatic juice will convert chymotrypsinogen

to the active form chymotrypsin. This would account for the increased proteolytic activity of the pancreatic juice as observed by Delezenne (*loc. cit.*) and Masakatsu Sato (*loc. cit.*).

S U M M A R Y.

1. The optimum activity of the proteolytic enzyme in Russell's viper venom is at about p_H 8.0 using gelatin and egg-albumin as substrates, while with casein as substrate it is in the neighbourhood of p_H 7.0. The protease in Russell's viper venom thus resembles trypsin.

2. The venom of cobra and of Russell's viper can digest Witte's peptone. The optimum activity of the peptidase contained in these venoms lies between p_H 8.2 to p_H 8.4. The peptidase in these venoms is therefore similar to erepsin.

3. The addition of cobra or of Russell's viper venom to trypsin (Merck) inhibits its proteolytic activity to a marked extent. These venoms, therefore, contain some trypsin inhibitor.

Our grateful thanks are due to Sir P. C. Rây for the laboratory facilities offered.